

Predictive factors for mortality in patients admitted to the intensive care unit

Factores predictivos de mortalidad en pacientes ingresados en la unidad de cuidados intensivos

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Abstract

Mortality prediction is a resource that allows optimized allocation of resources in the intensive care unit (ICU). Available scores provide an easy approach to mortality prediction in ICU patients. However, evidence has shown that these models are inadequate and imprecise for the intended purpose. Therefore, novel investigations are needed to optimize these models by including new variables. On the other hand, it has also been proposed to create new predictive models based on novel technology. Machine learning, artificial intelligence, models have been proposed as an alternative to solve this issue. However, more validation studies are needed to recommend further this novel approach toward mortality prediction. This review aims to analyze predictive mortality factors in the ICU context that can further optimize available scores or serve as an independent predictive factor.

Keywords: Intensive care unit, mortality, risk factors, predictive models, critical care.

Resumen

La predicción de la mortalidad es un recurso que permite optimizar la asignación de recursos en la unidad de cuidados intensivos (UCI). Las puntuaciones disponibles proporcionan un enfoque sencillo para la predicción de la mortalidad en pacientes de la UCI. Sin embargo, la evidencia ha demostrado que estos modelos son inadecuados e imprecisos para el propósito previsto. Por tanto, se necesitan investigaciones novedosas para optimizar estos modelos incluyendo nuevas variables. Por otro lado, también se ha propuesto crear nuevos modelos predictivos basados en tecnología novedosa. Se han propuesto diversos modelos de aprendizaje automático, inteligencia artificial y como alternativa para solucionar este problema. Sin embargo, se necesitan más estudios de validación para recomendar más este novedoso enfoque hacia la predicción de la mortalidad. Esta revisión tiene como objetivo analizar los factores predictivos de mortalidad en el contexto de la UCI que pueden optimizar aún más las puntuaciones disponibles o servir como un factor predictivo independiente.

Palabras clave: Unidad de cuidados intensivos, mortalidad, factores de riesgo, modelos predictivos, cuidados críticos.

Intensive care units (ICU) are the site for the management of critically ill patients, representing a large and expensive component of modern healthcare¹. It is estimated that 2% of the United States (US) population receives intensive care yearly². Furthermore, up to half of all US people experience ICU admission during their final year of life, and many of them die there³. With the increasing longevity and prevalence of chronic diseases like diabetes mellitus (DM), hypertension, heart failure, chronic kidney disease, and many others, the demand for ICUs is rising to colossal proportions^{4,5}. Moreover, the costs associated with ICU admissions are significantly high and variable depending on several factors. A day in the ICU may be as expensive as US\$10,000 when mechanical ventilation is included, thus, representing a significant financial burden for healthcare institutions⁶⁻⁸.

Although all developed countries have extensive ICU infrastructures, there is large variability regarding the supply of ICU beds between and within countries^{9,10}. Undeveloped countries tend to have less ICU availability than developed countries¹¹. Likewise, rural areas are less likely to have ICU beds available than urban areas¹². Although the reasons for such large variations are unclear, the epidemiology and location-specific demand for ICU admission may be the crucial determinants of these disparities¹³. However, it is undeniable that low-income countries lack ICU beds, and more than half of these countries lack published data regarding ICU capacity. For example, Nepal and Uganda have 16.7 and 1.0 ICU beds per million inhabitants, respectively, showing the magnitude of the deficit¹⁴.

Considering these limitations, it is vital to allocate these limited assets as efficiently as possible. Consequently, not every patient requiring ICU admission perceives this benefit¹⁵. Implementing predictive models for mortality makes it possible to determine which patients will benefit the most from the ICU at a cost-effective proportion¹⁶. Determining risk factors, specific diseases, and disease severity prior to and during hospitalization are only some of the means used by critical care physicians to choose, maintain, or readmit patients to the ICU. Although it may be perceived as unethical, proper patient selection for ICU admission results in higher ICU survival rates¹⁷. Patient screening and constant monitoring are the most important tools to optimize and make the most of the available resources, particularly in undeveloped countries. This review aims to analyze predictive mortality factors in the ICU context that can further optimize available scores or serve as an independent predictive factor.

Mortality predictors in intensive care units: can we do better?

Accurate prediction of the prognosis of patients admitted to the ICU is crucial for the patients and carers, as it allows them to dictate optimal clinical management, provide high-quality care, and predict the likelihood of re-admission. Identifying high-risk patients is paramount to allocating resources suitably and preventing morbidity and deaths^{18,19}. As a result, there is increasing interest in developing predictive mortality models that can improve the quality of care and decision-making. Unfortunately, most of these systems do not have sufficient power to predict outcomes accurately²⁰. Currently, several available scores are used in the ICU setting to help clinicians estimate mortality. The most common are the Simplified Acute Physiology Score II (SAPS-II), Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II (APACHE-II), and Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score²¹.

Each of these scales have advantages and disadvantages. For instance, the SOFA score uses clinical parameters and laboratory values, with the particular advantage over other scores that it can be recalculated every 24 hours to assess the evolution of the patient²². On the other hand, the SAPS-II and APACHE-II include age, history of severe organ failure or chronic condition, and type of admission, which are perfect to be assessed on newly admitted patients. These scores have perfect calibration and discrimination across a significant range of scenarios, determining the risk of mortality from 1% to 100%²³.

However, all these scores are focused on a momentary evaluation and less on the patient's previous states. Moreover, the APACHE-II was designed to fit all ICU populations, resulting in less accuracy than specific models²⁴. Similarly, the SAPS-II was built in a European/American environment, which can result in decreased accuracy when assessing other demographics²⁵. None of these scores are perfect for every setting, and none are illness-specific, but they provide a well-founded basis for new research²⁶. Ongoing investigations are trying to assess other potential risk factors that could increase the accuracy of mortality predictions in the ICU setting.

Firstly, age is a vital factor to consider, since the proportion of the elderly population has grown significantly in the past decades²⁷. The proportion of patients 80 years or older to be admitted into the ICU ranges between 7-25%, depending on the country^{28,29}. Initially, there was controversy regarding the role of advanced age as an independent risk factor, given that it is also associated with a higher prevalence of chronic diseases³⁰. Although some studies concluded that age was not predictive of poor prognosis within the ICU²⁹, more recent studies differ. Fuchs et al.³¹ found patients aged 75 years and older had a significantly higher mortality risk after adjusting for gender, comorbidities, disease severity, and other variables.

Nonetheless, whether age is an independent risk factor for in-hospital mortality remains unsettled. Elderly patients with a history of ICU admission have a significantly greater mortality risk at 3 years after discharge than the general population³². More recently, a prospective observational study found age was an independent risk factor only in the very elderly (80 years and above). Furthermore, other variables were associated with increased mortality in this group. Higher APACHE-II score, concurrent infection, infection location, development of acute kidney injury, and thrombocytopenia were better mortality predictors in the very elderly than in younger groups³³.

Separately, length of stay (LOS) is a temporal variable that measures the time between admission and discharge. Typically, longer LOS is suggestive of increased disease severity, slower satisfactory evolution, increased complications, and therapeutic failures. Conversely, shorter LOS is associated with more favorable post-discharge outcomes, lower readmission rates, and lower mortality³⁴. In this context, Moitra et al.³⁵ evaluated the association between LOS in the ICU and short and long-term mortality. Increased LOS was associated with a higher need for mechanical ventilation but not higher in-hospital mortality. However, for each day beyond seven days in the ICU, mortality risk at one year significantly increased, irrespective of the need for mechanical ventilation³⁵.

Furthermore, Bo et al.³⁶ conducted research to assess the association between several variables and ICU mortality. After univariate analysis, several factors like lower BMI, low serum albumin, functional impairment, and cognitive impairment were significantly associated with ICU mortality. Nonetheless, after multivariate analysis, the only predictive factors for in-hospital mortality were moderate-to-severe cognitive impairment, low BMI, higher APACHE II score, and lack of functional independence. The latter demonstrates that not only in-hospital variants are important to predict mortality but also previous patient conditions³⁶. Similarly, Wang et al.³⁷ more recently corroborated that lower BMI was associated with increased in-hospital mortality in ventilated patients. Moreover, analyses also reported that lower scores on the right or left quadriceps femoris muscle force were independently correlated with increased mortality.

Regarding chronic conditions like type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2), the available evidence is still conflicting about whether in-hospital mortality is increased in these patients³⁸. Although it would be logical to presume that diabetic patients have increased mortality risk, mainly because of their impaired immunity, evidence has failed to show this consistently³⁹. A meta-analysis reported DM2 was not associated with increased mortality in the ICU⁴⁰. Moreover, a recent meta-analysis regarding COVID-19 mortality failed to demonstrate increased mortality in the diabetic group compared to the non-diabetic group⁴¹. Despite the available evidence, controversy

remains since hyperglycemia has remained a relevant mortality predictor in critically ill patients, especially in non-diabetic populations^{42,43}.

Considering all the mentioned risk factors and the available predictive scores, mortality prediction still needs to be revised and remains a challenge. Available scores like the SAPS-II and APACHE-II have been modified several times to improve their predictive performance^{44,45}. However, several external validation studies have concluded that the most recent versions of these scores are not adequately calibrated, meaning that they fail to accurately predict negative outcomes, either by over or underestimation^{46,47}. To address this problem, a Super Learner model was developed as a nonparametric technique for constructing an optimal prediction algorithm from a given set of previous parameters provided by the user. Validation studies of this artificial intelligence learning technique have yielded impressive results⁴⁸.

According to Pirracchio et al.⁴⁹, this alternative provides improved performance for predicting ICU mortality than conventional scores with an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) of 0.94 (95% Confidence interval: 0.90-0.98). Furthermore, a recent study reported that the best-performing machine learning models achieved an AUROC of 0.977. In conjunction with conventional scoring systems, machine learning models can provide more useful information for mortality predictions. The only setback is that these models have a learning curve associated with the information given; therefore, each learning model is unique to each hospital or database⁵⁰. More research is needed to recommend machine learning models, but they seem to be the future of risk management and mortality prediction.

Conclusions

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ortality prediction is a resource that allows optimized allocation of resources in the ICU. The availability of ICU beds is a problem in developed and undeveloped countries; therefore, choosing a patient for ICU admission must follow a thorough process to establish if the patient can benefit from the hospitalization. Available scores provide an easy approach to mortality prediction in ICU patients. However, evidence has shown that these models are inadequate and imprecise for the intended purpose. Therefore, novel investigations are needed to optimize these models by including new variables. On the other hand, it has also been proposed to create new predictive models based on novel technology. Machine learning, artificial intelligence, models have been proposed as an alternative to solve this is-

sue. Available results are encouraging, considering that these machine learning models' predictive value and validity far exceed that of the conventional models. However, more validation studies are needed to recommend further this novel approach toward mortality prediction.

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